

Chemical constituents of *Argyreia argentea*, *Millingtonia hortensis* and *Pyrostegia venusta*

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Manuscript received 10 January 2001, revised 21 May 2001, accepted 6 August 2001

Isolation of five known compounds *n*-hentriacontanol, β -sitosterol, friedelin, epifriedelinol and epifriedelinol acetate from *Argyreia argentea* aerial parts; four known compounds nonacosanoic acid, ursolic acid, oleanolic acid and 6-methoxy-5,7,4'-trihydroxyflavone from *Millingtonia hortensis* flower, and four known compounds lupeol, betulin, betulinic acid and choline chloride from the stem bark of *Pyrostegia venusta* is reported.

Argyreia argentea Arn.ex Choisy (Convolvulaceae)¹, *Millingtonia hortensis* Linn., syn. *Bignonia suberosa* Roxb. (Bignoniaceae)^{1,3} and *Pyrostegia venusta* (Ker-Gawl) Miers, syn. *Bignonia venusta* Ker. Gawl, *Tecoma venusta* Len. (Bignoniaceae)¹ are found in Tripura State and their different parts are useful in folk medicine². Some attention to the chemistry of various parts of *M. hortensis*³ and *P. venusta*⁴ have already been focussed but *A. argentea* is investigated chemically for the first time by us. Here we report the isolation of five compounds from *A. argentea* and a few more compounds from *M. hortensis* and *P. venusta*, that are not reported earlier.

Air-dried aerial parts of *A. argentea* (3 kg) (collected from campus area of M. B. B. College, Agartala) were extracted with EtOAc in a Soxhlet extractor. The concentrated EtOAc extract was divided into basic and neutral parts by churning with 5% aq. citric acid solution and the neutral part (8.5 g) was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel (mesh 60–120). Elution of the column with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°)-benzene (14 : 1) mixture gave a white solid, which on crystallization from petroleum ether-CHCl₃ mixture gave granular crystals (15 mg), C₃₁H₆₄O (M⁺ 452), m.p. 88°. On acetylation with Ac₂O/Py it gave an acetate, m.p. 70°. The parent compound was identified as *n*-hentriacontanol by comparing its spectral (IR, ¹H NMR and EI-MS) data with those reported earlier⁵. Elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (6 : 1) mixture gave a white solid, which on crystallization from petroleum ether-chloroform mixture afforded colourless needles (30 mg), C₂₉H₅₀O (M⁺ 414), m.p. 136°, positive Liebermann Burchard test for sterols; acetate, m.p. 126°, identified as β -sitosterol by direct comparison (m.m.p. and superimposable IR) with an authentic sample. Elution of the column with

petroleum ether-benzene (4 : 1) mixture gave colourless crystals (10 mg), C₃₂H₅₄O₂ (M⁺ 470), m.p. 286°, positive Liebermann-Burchard test for triterpene and on hydrolysis with methanolic HCl gave deacetylated product, C₃₀H₅₂O (M⁺ 428), m.p. 279°. The parent compound was identified as 3-epifriedelinol acetate by comparison of its spectral (¹H NMR and EI-MS) data with that reported⁶ and by direct comparison (m.m.p. and co-TLC) with an authentic sample. Elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) mixture afforded a pale white solid, which on crystallization from CHCl₃-EtOAc mixture gave colourless needles (60 mg), C₃₀H₅₀O (M⁺ 426), m.p. 264°, positive Liebermann-Burchard test for triterpenes. The comparison of its IR, ¹H NMR, EI-MS and ¹³C NMR spectral data [δ (100 MHz, CDCl₃) 22.3 (C-1), 41.5 (C-2), 213.1 (C-3), 58.2 (C-4), 42.1 (C-5), 41.3 (C-6), 18.2 (C-7), 53.1 (C-8), 37.5 (C-9), 59.5 (C-10), 35.6 (C-11), 30.5 (C-12), 39.7 (C-13), 38.3 (C-14), 32.4 (C-15), 36.0 (C-16), 29.7 (C-17), 42.8 (C-18), 35.3 (C-19), 28.2 (C-20), 32.8 (C-21), 39.3 (C-22), 16.8 (C-23), 14.7 (C-24), 18.0 (C-25), 20.3 (C-26), 18.7 (C-27), 32.1 (C-28), 35.0 (C-29), 31.8 (C-30)] with literature⁷ as well as by comparison of its reduction product with methanolic NaBH₄ to 3-epifriedelinol, C₃₀H₅₂O, m.p. 279°, led to characterize this compound as friedelin (friedel-3-one). Elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 4) mixture afforded colourless needles (50 mg), C₃₀H₅₂O (M⁺ 428), m.p. 280°, positive Liebermann-Burchard test for triterpene, identified as 3-epifriedelinol⁸ by comparing its m.p. and spectral data with those reported earlier^{6,8}.

Fresh air-dried flowers of *M. hortensis* (3 kg) collected from local area were extracted with EtOAc in a Soxhlet extractor and the extract was concentrated under reduced pres-

sure. The concentrated extract was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel. Elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) mixture afforded a solid which on crystallization from benzene-CHCl₃ mixture gave colourless granular crystals (30 mg), C₂₉H₅₈O₂ (M⁺ 438), m.p. 89°, Me-ester, C₃₀H₆₀O₂, m.p. 67°, identified as nonacosanoic acid by comparing the m.p. and spectral data with those reported earlier⁹. Elution of the column with CHCl₃-Me₂CO (9 : 1) mixture gave a solid which on further column chromatography afforded two compounds – one compound as colourless needles (90 mg), C₃₀H₄₈O₃ (M⁺ 456), m.p. 280–282°, acetate, C₃₂H₅₀O₄ (M⁺ 498), m.p. 284°, identified as ursolic acid by comparing the spectral data of parent compound and its acetate with those reported earlier¹⁰, and another as colourless needles (30 mg), C₃₀H₄₈O₃ (M⁺ 456), m.p. 305°, acetate, C₃₂H₅₀O₄ (M⁺ 498), m.p. 267°, identified as oleanolic acid¹⁰ by direct comparison with an authentic sample (in co-TLC and m.m.p.). Elution of the column with CHCl₃-Me₂CO (7.5 : 2.5) mixture afforded yellow needles (60 mg), C₁₆H₁₂O₆ (M⁺ 300), m.p. 280°, λ_{max} (MeOH) 306 (log ε 4.04) and 344 (3.15) nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3400 (OH), 1660 (>C=CCO), 1615 cm⁻¹ (aromatic ring); ¹H NMR δ (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) 3.72 (3H, s, MeO-6), 6.56 (1H, s, H-8), 6.74 (1H, s, H-3), 6.90 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, H-3', 5'), 7.89 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, H-2', 6'), 9.6–11.0 (2H, br s, disappeared on treatment with D₂O, HO-7,4') and 13.04 (1H, br s, disappeared on treatment with D₂O, HO-5); ¹³C NMR δ (100 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) 163.7 (C-2), 102.3 (C-3), 182.0 (C-4), 152.7 (C-5), 131.4 (C-6), 157.7 (C-7), 94.3 (C-8), 152.4 (C-9), 103.8 (C-10), 121.2 (C-1'), 128.4 (C-2'), 115.9 (C-3'), 161.3 (C-4'), 115.9 (C-5'), 128.4 (C-6'), 59.9 (MeO-6); EIMS *m/z* (rel. int.) 300 [M]⁺ (100), 285 [M-15]⁺ (67), 282 (52), 271 [M-CHO]⁺ (15), 270 (25), 257 [M-43]⁺ (82), 167 (17), 153 (14), 118 (27) and 43 (98); characterized as 6-methoxy-5,7,4'-trihydroxyflavone (hispidulin or dinatin)^{3,11}. This compound was reported earlier from this plant and from other plants but ¹H, ¹³C NMR and MS data of the parent compound were not reported elsewhere.

Air-dried stems (2 kg) of *P. venusta* collected from the local area was extracted with EtOAc in a Soxhlet extractor and the extract was concentrated under reduced pressure. The concentrated gummy extract was treated with 2 *N* NaOH and the alkaline aqueous extract was acidified with 2 *N* HCl and extracted with CHCl₃. The concentrated CHCl₃ extract was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel and the column was eluted with organic solvents of increasing polarity. Elution of the column with benzene gave colourless needles (20 mg), C₃₀H₅₀O (M⁺ 426), m.p. 215°, [α]_D +25°

(CHCl₃), acetate, C₃₂H₅₂O₂ (M⁺ 468), m.p. 212°, characterized as lupeol by comparison of its physical constants and spectral data with literature¹² as well as by direct comparison (co-TLC and m.m.p.) with an authentic sample. Elution of the column with benzene-CHCl₃ (9 : 1) mixture afforded colourless crystals (15 mg), C₃₀H₅₀O₂ (M⁺ 442), m.p. 250°, diacetate, C₃₄H₅₄O₆ (M⁺ 526), m.p. 216°, characterized as betulin¹³ by direct comparison (m.m.p. and co-TLC) with an authentic sample. Elution of the column with benzene-CHCl₃ (8 : 2) mixture gave colourless needles (30 mg), C₃₀H₄₈O₃ (M⁺ 456), m.p. 315°, methyl ester, C₃₁H₅₀O₃ (M⁺ 470), m.p. 220°, identified as betulinic acid¹³ by direct comparison (m.m.p. and co-TLC) with an authentic sample. Elution of the column with CHCl₃-MeOH (1 : 3) mixture gave colourless crystals (70 mg), C₅H₁₄N⁺OC₁⁻ (MH⁺ 140), m.p. 305°, ν_{max} (KBr) 3400 and 1370 cm⁻¹ (OH); δ (400 MHz, D₂O) 1.32 (2H, t, N⁺CH₂), 3.30 (9H, t, N⁺(CH₃)₃), 4.78 (2H, t, CH₂O, merged with the peak of D₂O); FAB⁺ *m/z* 140 [M+H]⁺ (100%), identified as choline chloride¹⁴ by its spectral studies and direct comparison (m.m.p., and co-TLC) with an authentic sample.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to I.I.C.B., Jadavpur, Kolkata, for IR spectra and one of the authors (U.C.D) is thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for a Senior Research Fellowship.

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